

IC Modelling and Analysis in Geotechnical Engineering

Model 20

Contents:

IC MAGE M20 is a user-defined model for PLAXIS, developed using the IC MAGE UMIP framework. The model builds upon the SANICLAY model with bounding surface formulation proposed by Seidalinov and Taiebat (2014) featuring both isotropic and kinematic hardening of the bounding surface, which retains the same elliptical shape as the Modified Cam-Clay yield surface, and adopts a projection centre updating at stress reversal. To enhance the simulation of clay response under cyclic loading, the model implements: i) a modified evolution of the hardening modulus, ii) a novel damage mechanism driven by cumulative dissipated energy, and iii) a formulation for describing stiffness at small strains.

Disclaimer:

IC MAGE soil models undergo extensive testing and validation but can never be guaranteed to be free of errors. IC MAGE soil models are employed at the users' own risk and the authors of these models cannot be held responsible or liable for any errors arising from their application.

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IC MAGE M20

An energy based SANICLAY model for cyclic clay behaviour

PARAMETERS

P1	μ	$-1 < \mu < 0.5$	Poisson's ratio
P2	λ	> 0	Slope of the compression line
P3	κ	> 0	Initial slope of the swelling line
P4	M_c	> 0	Stress ratio at Critical State in triaxial compression
P5	M_e	> 0	Stress ratio at Critical State in triaxial extension
P6	N	> 0	Shape factor for the bounding surface
P7	h_0	> 0	Initial hardening modulus scalar
P8	a_d	≥ 0	Reference damage rate
P9	C	≥ 0	Rate of evolution of anisotropy
P10	x	≥ 0	Saturation limit of anisotropy
P11	s_Y	≥ 1	Size of the elastic nucleus
P12	OCR_1	$< -1, \geq 0$	OCR at the ground surface and up to a depth of d_1
P13	d_1		Depth at which $OCR = OCR_1$
P14	OCR_2		OCR at a depth of d_2
P15	d_2		Depth at which $OCR = OCR_1$
P16	<i>DepthSwitch</i>	0,1,2	Defines vertical direction and coordinate for d_1 and d_2 : global x (0), y (1) or z (2)
P17	e_0 or v_1	$\neq 0$	Initial void ratio (> 0) or volume at 1 kPa for NC samples (< 0)
P18	$K_{min} (FL^{-2})$	≥ 0	Minimum bulk stiffness
P19	<i>PlasticTol</i>	≥ 0	Tolerance for integrating the plastic part
P20	<i>MaxPlasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	Maximum number of steps for integrating plastic part
P21	<i>OutputControl</i>	0,1,2,3,4	Controls the desired output by the model
P22	$p_r (FL^{-2})$	≥ 0	Reference pressure for G_0
P23	A	≥ 0	Elastic stiffness parameter for G_0
P24	n	$0 \leq n < 1$	Elastic stiffness parameter for effect of confinement on G_0
P25	m	$0 \leq n < 1$	Elastic stiffness parameter for OCR effect on G_0

P26	E_a	≥ 1	Activation Energy
P27	δ	≥ 0	Energy dissipation control
P27	γ		Cyclic stress-dependency factor
P29	$b_{sr,ref}$	≥ 1	Reference stress ratio
P28	<i>EnergyCalc</i>	0,1 → 9, 11 → 19	No energy calculated if 0, see UMIP for other options

(*) only used if P1=0.

DEFAULT VALUES

If set to 0.0, the following defaults values will be assumed:

P19	<i>Plastic_{tot}</i>	1×10^{-4}
P20	<i>MaxPlasticSteps</i>	10000

HARDENING PARAMETERS

HP1	<i>Init_{var}</i>	Initialisation variable (required by UMIP)
HP2	e_0	Initial void ratio
HP3	e_i	Current void ratio
HP4	p_0	Current size of the bounding surface
HP5	α_{xx}	Axis of the yield surface (x -component)
HP6	α_{yy}	Axis of the yield surface (y -component)
HP7	α_{zz}	Axis of the yield surface (z -component)
HP8	α_{xy}	Axis of the yield surface (xy -component)
HP9	α_{yz}	Axis of the yield surface (yz -component)
HP10	α_{zx}	Axis of the yield surface (xz -component)
HP11	p_c	Mean effective stress at the projection centre
HP12	$s_{xx,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (x -component)
HP13	$s_{yy,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (y -component)
HP14	$s_{zz,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (z -component)
HP15	$s_{xy,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (xy -component)
HP16	$s_{yz,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (yz -component)
HP17	$s_{zx,c}$	Deviatoric stress state at the projection centre (xz -component)
HP18	X	Ratio between stresses at the projection centre and projection point
HP19	d	Damage parameter
HP20	ϵ_{xx}^p	Plastic strain state (x -component)

HP21	ε_{yy}^p	Plastic strain state (<i>y</i> -component)
HP22	ε_{zz}^p	Plastic strain state (<i>z</i> -component)
HP23	γ_{xy}^p	Plastic strain state (<i>xy</i> -component)
HP24	γ_{yz}^p	Plastic strain state (<i>yz</i> -component)
HP25	γ_{xz}^p	Plastic strain state (<i>xz</i> -component)
HP26	E_d^p	Plastic deviatoric strain
HP27	ε_{vol}^p	Plastic volumetric strain
HP28	G_{tan}	Current elastic shear stiffness
HP29	K_{tan}	Current elastic bulk stiffness
HP30	J	Deviatoric stress (second invariant of stress tensor)
HP31	θ	Lode's angle (third invariant of stress tensor)
HP32	N_{rev}	Number of detected reversals
HP33	\bar{p}	Mean effective stress at the image point
HP34	\bar{s}_{xx}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (<i>x</i> -component)
HP35	\bar{s}_{yy}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (<i>y</i> -component)
HP36	\bar{s}_{zz}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (<i>z</i> -component)
HP37	\bar{s}_{xy}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (<i>xy</i> -component)
HP38	\bar{s}_{yz}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (<i>yz</i> -component)
HP39	\bar{s}_{zx}	Deviatoric stress state at the image point (<i>xz</i> -component)
HP40	b	Distance ratio <i>b</i> between image stress and stress state
HP41	Λ	Plastic multiplier
HP42	K_p	Hardening modulus
HP43	G_0	Shear modulus at small strains
HP44	b_{sr}	Value of distance ratio <i>b</i> at last stress reversal
HP45	$\varepsilon_{xx,rev}$	Strain tensor at last shear reversal (<i>x</i> component)
HP46	$\varepsilon_{yy,rev}$	Strain tensor at last shear reversal (<i>y</i> component)
HP47	$\varepsilon_{zz,rev}$	Strain tensor at last shear reversal (<i>z</i> component)
HP48	$\gamma_{xy,rev}$	Strain tensor at last shear reversal (<i>xy</i> component)
HP49	$\gamma_{yz,rev}$	Strain tensor at last shear reversal (<i>yz</i> component)
HP50	$\gamma_{xz,rev}$	Strain tensor at last shear reversal (<i>xz</i> component)
HP51	$\sigma_{xx,rev}$	Stress tensor at last shear reversal (<i>x</i> component)

HP52	$\sigma_{yy,rev}$	Stress tensor at last shear reversal (y component)
HP53	$\sigma_{zz,rev}$	Stress tensor at last shear reversal (z component)
HP54	$\tau_{xy,rev}$	Stress tensor at last shear reversal (xy component)
HP55	$\tau_{yz,rev}$	Stress tensor at last shear reversal (yz component)
HP56	$\tau_{xz,rev}$	Stress tensor at last shear reversal (xz component)
HP57	$E_{def,i}^i$	Current deformation level within cycle i
HP58	$E_{acc,i}$	Current accumulated energy within cycle i
HP59	$E_{el,i}$	Current elastic energy within cycle i
HP60	$E_{diss,i}$	Current dissipated energy within cycle i
HP61	E_{diss}^*	Cumulative dissipated energy from beginning of loading
HP62	$E_{diss, eff}^*$	Cumulative dissipated energy from beginning of loading beyond activation energy
HP63	f_{act}	Activation factor
HP64 – HP96		Energy calculation (only if P27 $Energy_{calc}$ is set to ≥ 1.0)

MODEL FORMULATION

1. Elastic behaviour

1.1 Large strains

The following hypoelastic relations, adopting a non-linear variation of the bulk modulus (K) and a constant Poisson's ratio (μ), are used:

$$K = \nu \cdot \frac{p}{\kappa} \quad (1)$$

$$G = \frac{3K(1 - 2\mu)}{2(1 + \mu)} \quad (2)$$

where $\nu = 1 + e$ is the current specific volume.

1.2 Small strains

If Poisson's ratio is set to zero ($P1 = 0$), the small strain elastic shear modulus is evaluated following Viggiani and Atkinson (1995):

$$\frac{G}{p_r} = A \left(\frac{p}{p_r} \right)^n \cdot R_0^m \quad (3)$$

where A , n and m are material parameters, p_r is the reference pressure so that parameters A , n and m are dimensionless with a value depending on p_r , while $R_0 = p_0/p$ represents OCR in terms of mean pressure, which must be initialized following Section 6.

Furthermore, the elastic bulk modulus is evaluated directly from the slope of the swelling line (P3) as:

$$K = \frac{1 + e}{k} p \quad (4)$$

where e is the current void ratio.

2. Projection rule

The model relies on the behaviour of the soil being assessed at the projection point. This is the 'image' of the current stress state projected onto the bounding surface and can be determined, in terms of isotropic and deviatoric components as:

$$\bar{p} = p_c + b(p - p_c) \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}} = \mathbf{s}_c + b(\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}_c) \quad (6)$$

with the subscript 'c' referring to the stress conditions at the projection centre. The mean effective stress and the deviatoric stress tensor at the projection centre are hardening parameters. Note that, according to this definition of b , the value of this quantity varies between infinity for $p = p_c$ and 1 for $p = \bar{p}$, i.e. reduces gradually as the current stress point approaches the projection point implying $b=1$.

The value of b can be determined following the approach outlined in Seidalinov & Taiebat (2014), taking the positive root of the quadratic equation:

$$Ab^2 + Bb + C = 0 \quad (7)$$

with

$$A = A_1 + \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2} \boldsymbol{\alpha} : \boldsymbol{\alpha} \right) A_2 \quad (8)$$

$$B = B_1 + \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right)B_2 \quad (9)$$

$$C = C_1 + \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right)C_2 \quad (10)$$

and

$$A_1 = \frac{3}{2}(\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}_c):(\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}_c) - 3(p - p_c)[(\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}_c):\boldsymbol{\alpha}] + \frac{3}{2}(p - p_c)^2\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (11)$$

$$B_1 = 3(\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}_c):\mathbf{s}_c - 3[p_c\mathbf{s} + (p - 2p_c)\mathbf{s}_c]:\boldsymbol{\alpha} + 3p_c(p - p_c)\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (12)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{3}{2}\mathbf{s}_c:\mathbf{s}_c - 3p_c\mathbf{s}_c:\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \frac{3}{2}p_c^2\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha} \quad (13)$$

$$A_2 = (p - p_c)^2 \quad (14)$$

$$B_2 = (2p_c - p_0)(p - p_c) \quad (15)$$

$$C_2 = p_c(p_c - p_0) \quad (16)$$

Therefore:

$$b = \frac{-B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC}}{2A} \quad (17)$$

and thus:

$$b = \frac{-B + \text{sign}(A) \cdot \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC}}{2A} \quad (18)$$

3. Bounding surface

The bounding surface is given by:

$$F = \frac{3}{2}(\bar{\mathbf{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}):(\bar{\mathbf{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) - \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot \bar{p}(p_0 - \bar{p}) = 0 \quad (19)$$

where $p = \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma})/3$ and $\mathbf{s} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - p\mathbf{I}$, with the notation \bar{p} and $\bar{\mathbf{s}}$ designating these quantities at the projection point, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ is the tensor defining the axis of the bounding surface, while p_0 is its size.

The gradient of the bounding surface, given that N is assumed to be a constant value (i.e. the shape of the bounding surface in the deviatoric plane is a circle), can be determined using

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = 3(\bar{\mathbf{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) + \frac{1}{3}\bar{p} \cdot \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\bar{\mathbf{r}}:\bar{\mathbf{r}}\right)\mathbf{I} \quad (20)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{s}}}{\bar{p}} = \frac{\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} - \bar{p}\mathbf{I}}{\bar{p}} \quad (21)$$

4. Plastic potential

The plastic potential is given by a similar shape to that of the plastic potential but with a different value of the inclination:

$$G = \frac{3}{2}(\bar{\mathbf{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}):(\bar{\mathbf{s}} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) - \left(M(\theta)^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot \bar{p}(p_0 - \bar{p}) = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $M(\theta)$ is now a quantity dependent on the Lode's angle according to Argyris et al. (1974):

$$M(\theta) = \frac{2c}{(1+c)-(1-c)\cos(3\theta)} M_c \quad (23)$$

with $c = M_e/M_c$, in which M_c is the stress ratio at Critical State in triaxial compression and M_e is the stress ratio at Critical State in triaxial extension.

The Lode's angle can be determined using:

$$\cos(3\theta) = \sqrt{6} \cdot \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^3) \quad (24)$$

with

$$\bar{\mathbf{n}} = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}}{\sqrt{(\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\alpha})}} \quad (25)$$

and where $\theta = 0^\circ$ corresponds to triaxial compression and $\theta = 60^\circ$ corresponds to triaxial extension.

The gradients of the plastic potential are given by:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = 3(\bar{s} - \bar{p}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) + \frac{1}{3}\bar{p} \cdot \left(M^2 - \frac{3}{2}\bar{\mathbf{r}} : \bar{\mathbf{r}} \right) \mathbf{I} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \quad (26)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial \theta} = 6M^2 \cdot \bar{p}(p_0 - \bar{p}) \cdot \frac{(1-c)\sin(3\theta)}{(1+c) - (1-c)\cos(3\theta)} \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \frac{-3 \left[\bar{\mathbf{n}}^2 - \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^3)\bar{\mathbf{n}} - 1/3 \cdot \mathbf{I} \cdot \left(1 + \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^2\boldsymbol{\alpha}) - \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^3) \cdot \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{n}}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \right) \right]}{\bar{p} \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - \boldsymbol{\alpha})} \cdot \sin(3\theta)} \quad (28)$$

5. Plastic behaviour

The following quantity related to isotropic hardening is introduced:

$$\bar{p}_0 = \frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} = \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \quad (29)$$

while the equivalent for rotational hardening is given by:

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} = \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \cdot C \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right)^2 \left| \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \right| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha})} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^b - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \quad (30)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}^b = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \min(N, M_e) \cdot \mathbf{n}_x \quad (31)$$

and

$$\mathbf{n}_x = \frac{\left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}}{x}\right) - \alpha}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}}{x} - \alpha\right) : \left(\frac{\bar{\mathbf{r}}}{x} - \alpha\right)}} \quad (32)$$

The hardening modulus for states on the bounding surface can be determined using:

$$\bar{A} = -\left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_0} \bar{p}_0 + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha} : \bar{\alpha}\right) \quad (33)$$

with

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial p_0} = -\bar{p} \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2} \alpha : \alpha\right) \quad (34)$$

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \alpha} = -3\bar{p}(\bar{s} - p_0 \alpha) \quad (35)$$

The current value of the hardening modulus can then be determined through an additional correction:

$$A = \bar{A} + \frac{h \cdot p_0^3}{\langle \frac{b}{b-1} - s_Y \rangle} \quad (36)$$

where b is defined as outlined above under *Projection rule*, s_Y is a parameter defining the size of the elastic locus (larger values of s_Y mean the denominator is negative and hence taken as 0, which leads to $A \rightarrow \infty$ and thus to $\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p \rightarrow 0$) and h is dependent on the hardening parameter d :

$$h = \frac{h_0}{1 + d \left(\frac{b}{b_{sr}}\right)^\delta} \quad (37)$$

In Eq. (37), the variable b_{sr} is defined as the value of b recorded at the last stress reversal. Therefore, the ratio $b/b_{sr} \geq 1$ varies significantly with the evolution of cycles. Specifically, at stress reversal b/b_{sr} is equal to 1. Immediately after, the ratio b/b_{sr} becomes very large, thus, h reduces for increasing the material stiffness. As shearing progresses within each half-cycle, $\frac{b}{b_{sr}}$ reduces, decreasing the material stiffness. The parameter δ controls the effect of $\frac{b}{b_{sr}}$ on the rate at which h evolves during loading. Larger values lead to faster recovery of h after stress reversal, producing narrower loops and lower damping. This effect is only noticeable with damage d active (see Sec. 5.4).

The plastic multiplier can be obtained using:

$$\Lambda = \frac{\frac{\partial F^T}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} [D] \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{\frac{\partial F^T}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} [D] \frac{\partial G}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} + A} \quad (38)$$

5. Hardening rules

5.1. Isotropic hardening

The hardening rule controlling the change in the size of the bounding surface is given as:

$$\Delta p_0 = \Delta \varepsilon_{vol}^p \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot tr \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \quad (39)$$

which can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta p_o = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{p}_0 \quad (38)$$

5.2. Rotational hardening

The kinematic hardening is controlled by:

$$\Delta \alpha = \langle \Lambda \rangle \frac{\nu}{\lambda - \kappa} \cdot C \cdot \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right)^2 \left| \text{tr} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{G}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} \right) \right| \cdot \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}) : (\bar{\mathbf{r}} - x \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha})} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\alpha}^b - \boldsymbol{\alpha}) \quad (39)$$

and can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta \alpha = \langle \Lambda \rangle \cdot \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} \quad (40)$$

5.3. Projection centre evolution

Following Seidalinov (2018), the projection centre updates at each stress reversal and evolves with bounding surface evolution to ensure consistency.

Condition for stress reversal detection is defined as $\Lambda \leq 0$. In this case, a new Projection Centre is created and set such that it takes the coordinates of the current stress point:

$$p_c = p \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_c = \mathbf{s} \quad (42)$$

Moreover, to accommodate the evolution of p_0 and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, in the absence of stress reversal, the evolution of the position of the projection centre is determined as:

$$\Delta p_c = \frac{p_c}{p_0} \cdot \Delta p_0 \quad (43)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{s}_c = \frac{\mathbf{s}_c}{p_0} \cdot \Delta p_0 + \left[p_c \cdot \Delta \boldsymbol{\alpha} - X \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} \cdot \frac{p_c \cdot (p_0 - p_c) \cdot \frac{3}{2}}{\sqrt{\left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2} \boldsymbol{\alpha} : \boldsymbol{\alpha} \right) \cdot p_c \cdot (p_0 - p_c)}} \mathbf{n}_c \right] \quad (44)$$

with X being a scalar quantity evaluated as:

$$X = \frac{\left[\frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) : (\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\left[\frac{3}{2} (\mathbf{s}_b - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) : (\mathbf{s}_b - \mathbf{s}_\alpha) \right]} \quad (45)$$

where \mathbf{s}_b is a deviatoric stress tensor on the bounding surface along

$$\mathbf{n}_c = \frac{\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha}{|\mathbf{s}_c - \mathbf{s}_\alpha|} \quad (46)$$

for a given PC and $\mathbf{s}_\alpha = p_c \boldsymbol{\alpha}$.

5.4. Damage

As a stiffness degradation mechanism, an energy-based damage driven by the dissipated energy, which is defined as the area enclosed by the stress-strain hysteresis loop, is introduced. To enable its continuous evaluation under arbitrary loading conditions, the algorithm by Taborda et al. (2016) is

adopted and is summarised below. Let $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ denote the second-order stress and strain tensors, with subscripts 'i' and 'rev' referring to the current states and to those at last reversal, respectively, while (\cdot) denotes the trace product. The dissipated energy $E_{\text{diss},i}$ between the last reversal $(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{rev}}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{rev}})$ and the current step i $(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i)$ is given by:

$$E_{\text{diss},i} = E_{\text{acc},i} - E_{\text{el},i} \quad (47)$$

where the accumulated energy $E_{\text{acc},i}$ and elastic energy $E_{\text{el},i}$ are calculated using:

$$E_{\text{acc},i} = \int_{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{rev}}}^{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{rev}}) : d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (48)$$

$$E_{\text{el},i} = \frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{\text{rev}}) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{\text{rev}}) \quad (49)$$

Furthermore, as a damage driving variable, the effective dissipated energy rate is introduced:

$$\Delta E_{\text{diss}}^{\text{eff}} = H(E_{\text{diss},i,\text{max}} - E_a) \cdot \Delta E_{\text{diss},i} \quad (50)$$

where E_a is the activation energy (per half-cycle) and $H(\cdot)$ the Heaviside function, ensuring that damage initiates only when E_a is exceeded. The activation condition is evaluated using the maximum dissipated energy per half-cycle $E_{\text{diss},i,\text{max}}$ attained during loading history. This reflects the assumption that, once E_a is exceeded, all subsequent dissipated-energy increments contribute to damage, even when $E_{\text{diss},i}$ falls below E_a .

The incremental form of the proposed damage variable is

$$\Delta d = a_d^{1+(b_{\text{sr}}-1)\gamma} \left(\frac{1}{b_{\text{sr}}} - \frac{1}{b_{\text{sr,ref}}} \right) \Delta E_{\text{diss}}^{\text{eff}} \leq 0 \quad (51)$$

where b_{sr} serves effectively as a proxy for cyclic stress amplitude (Palmieri and Taiebat, 2024), a_d and γ are model parameters controlling the reference damage rate and its cyclic stress-dependency, respectively, and $b_{\text{sr,ref}}$ is a parameter representative of the reference stress ratio used for calibration. The cyclic stress-dependency vanishes at reversal ($b_{\text{sr}} = 1$), preventing damage during monotonic unloading from normally consolidated conditions. For $\gamma = 0$, the damage rate becomes independent of the cyclic stress, while setting $a_d = \gamma = 0$ deactivated the damage mechanism. As a calibration strategy, one may first calibrate a_d at a reference CSR corresponding to a specific $b_{\text{sr,ref}}$. Once these two are defined, γ can be determined to capture the rate of damage at different CSR.

6. Initialisation

The axis of the bounding surface is initialised by setting it to coincide with the initial stress state, i.e:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \frac{s}{p} = \frac{\sigma - pI}{p} \quad (52)$$

The size of the bounding surface can then be determined based on the parameters defining OCR:

$-1 \leq \text{OCR} < 0$ and $0 < \text{OCR} < 1$: Not possible.

OCR = 0: The initialisation is based on information provided via a text file with the following format:

Location: C:\icmage\input.icmageM18.txt

Format:

Ndata	Ctype	Ntype
Coord1	Data1	

Coord2 Data2
 ...
 CoordN DataN

where $Ndata$ is the number of points given, $Ctype$ is the switch defining which coordinate is being given in the list below ($Ctype = 0$ for x , $Ctype = 1$ for y and $Ctype = 2$ for z), while $Ntype$ determines whether the data given relates to OCR in terms of p' ($Ntype = 0$) or OCR in terms of σ'_v ($Ntype = 1$).

Based on the specified value of OCR, the following operations are carried out:

OCR = 1: The initial stress state is on the bounding surface.

If $K_0 = 1$, then $p_0 = p_{ini}$.

If $K_0 \neq 1$, then to calculate p_0 the current stress state needs to be substituted into the equation for the bounding surface (i.e. the initial stress state corresponds to the projected stress state), which can then be solved for p_0 :

$$F = \frac{3}{2}(\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha}):(\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha}) - \left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot p_{ini}(p_0 - p_{ini}) = 0 \quad (47)$$

$$\Rightarrow p_0 = p_{ini} + \frac{\frac{3}{2}(\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha}):(\mathbf{s}_{ini} - p_{ini}\boldsymbol{\alpha})}{\left(N^2 - \frac{3}{2}\boldsymbol{\alpha}:\boldsymbol{\alpha}\right) \cdot p_{ini}}$$

OCR > 1: $p_0 = OCR \cdot p_{ini}$.

OCR < -1: $\sigma_{v,max} = OCR \cdot \sigma_{v,ini}$, where $\sigma_{v,ini}$ is the current vertical effective stress and $\sigma_{v,max}$ is the maximum vertical effective stress. To complete the characterisation of the stress state at maximum vertical effective stress, the horizontal effective needs to be calculated:

$$\sigma_{h,max} = (1 - \sin \varphi) \cdot \sigma_{v,max} \quad (48)$$

This stress state is then introduced into the expression for the bounding surface to determine its size.

OCR can vary with depth as shown in Figure 1, where the coordinate used to characterise this variation is defined by $P16 \text{ DepthSwitch}$. If $P16$ is set to 0.0, then the variation is along x_c , if $P16$ is set to 1.0, then the variation is along y_c and if $P16$ is set to 2.0, then the variation is along z_c (3D analyses only).

Figure 1: Variation of OCR with depth.

The void ratio is initialised based on the value of e_0 provided by $P17$ if this is a positive value. If negative, then $v_1 = -P17$ and the void ratio is initialised as follows:

If $OCR = 1$, i.e. the stress state is on the isotropic virgin compression line, then:

$$v = v_1 - \lambda \cdot \ln p \quad (55)$$

In every other permissible case, the stress state is on a swelling line and:

$$v = v_1 - \lambda \cdot \ln p_0 + \kappa \cdot (\ln p_0 - \ln p) \quad (56)$$

To avoid singularities, the projection centre is initialised to 99% of the initial stress conditions, i.e. $p_c = 0.99 \cdot p_{ini}$ and $s_c = 0.99 \cdot s_{ini}$. This creates a sufficiently large distance between the projection centre and the current stress state to enable the determination of the projection point, without triggering excessive plasticity within the first loading steps.

MODEL USAGE

1. *P21 OutputControl* determines the level of output desired from the model integration:

<i>P21 = 0</i>	Full output with details on the integration of the model and warnings (default).
<i>P21 = 1</i>	Full output with details on the integration of the model but without warnings.
<i>P21 = 2</i>	Brief output consisting only of the progress of the calculation (step and iteration) and warnings.
<i>P21 = 3</i>	Brief output consisting only of the progress of the calculation (step and iteration) but without warnings.
<i>P21 = 4</i>	No output will be produced

2. If *P22 EnergyCalc* is set to 1.0, the UMIP will add 33 new hardening parameters to the constitutive model to calculate and store energy-related quantities. More information can be found in the documentation of the UMIP but of greatest interest are the current damping ratio (HP68), the secant shear stiffness (HP69) and the secant shear stiffness (HP70). This module is particularly useful if the model is being used for pseudo-static or dynamic analyses. Note that the use of this option increases slightly memory and processing requirements.

3. A text file input approach is available to define values of parameters which could not be included in the list of parameters due to PLAXIS' limit of 50 model parameters. To use this feature, a file called *M01.settings.txt* should be placed within the folder *C:\icmage* with the following contents:

Control parameter			Default value	Description
F01	<i>MinPlasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	2	Minimum no of plastic integration steps
F02	<i>MaxPlasticSteps</i>	≥ 0	10000	Maximum no of plastic integration steps
F03	<i>PlasticTol</i>	≥ 0	1×10^{-3}	Plastic integration tolerance
F04	<i>PlasticHPControl</i>	0,1	1	0 – changes in elastic hardening parameters do not affect elastic integration 1 – changes in elastic hardening parameters affect elastic integration
F05	<i>YieldTol</i>	≥ 0	1×10^{-6}	Yield tolerance
F06	<i>ApexTol (FL⁻²)</i>	≥ 0	0.1	Apex tolerance
F07	<i>YieldMax</i>	≥ 0	1000.0	Maximum value of yield function
F08	<i>PlasticUnload</i>	≥ 0	1×10^{-6}	Plastic unloading tolerance
F09	<i>Solution Control</i>	0,1	1	0 – the stiffness matrix is generated only at the start of the phase

Control parameter			Default value	Description
				1 – the stiffness matrix is generated at the start of every step
F10	<i>Stiffness scalar</i>	≥ 10	120	Scalar used to increase the elastic matrix in percentage. Larger values improve the stability of the solution but slows down convergence.
F11	<i>Unloading control</i>	0, 1	0	0 – the stiffness matrix is generated based on current elastic stiffness 1 – the stiffness matrix is generated based on maximum elastic stiffness
F12	<i>Undrained ν</i>	$-1.0 \leq \nu < 0.5$	0.495	Undrained Poisson's ratio to use

Note that, with the exception of F04, F09 and F11, if a value of zero is used, then the default value (or the one in the graphical input if it has been specified) will be used. Since a value of 0 is a possible value for F04, F09 and F11, the desired value must always be specified. Moreover, the file must always have the full list of parameters being given as the code expects to find a column with 12 values, returning an error if a smaller number of parameters is found. Lastly, **note that parameters specified via the GUI will always take precedence.**

PUBLICATIONS

More details on the formulation, parameter calibration, model validation, and application to a boundary value problem can be found in Palmieri and Taborda (2025, 2026a, 2026b).

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